

Study: Mapping mobility: a community vehicle to carbon reduction and pollution abatement.

How to get involved - a guide on participation!

This project is interested in where active travel currently takes place in Rugeley. We would like to work with the community to collect this data, using an application called Map My Tracks. We also would like to offer members of the community the opportunity to join our 'citizen science training program' which will teach you the theory behind how the project works, as well as the practical skills needed to complete the analysis. You should make sure you have read the project information sheet and consent forms.

How the process works (ALL PARTICIPANTS):

1. Understanding the project:

You read the information sheet, which explains the purpose of the project, how your data will be handled and used and the different levels of engagement that are possible. You can choose to simply contribute data, or you can decide to participate in the full citizen science training program. You should ensure you are comfortable with how the project works and ask as many questions as you would like to ask.

2. Consenting to participate:

Once you are happy that you understand the project, you will then be asked to sign a consent form. The consent form you sign will depend on the level of engagement you are opting in to. If you want to simply *contribute* to the data, you will sign **consent form A**. If you would like to take part in the full *citizen science training program*, you should sign **consent form B**. Consenting to the study is necessary. If you have decided to elect a 'buddy' to participate on your behalf, both of you will need to sign the appropriate consent form.

This section is for those opting to contribute to the active travel dataset. You should also read this if you are taking part in the citizen science training program.

3. Preparing to participate:

You can prepare in these easy steps:

- All individuals will download the free application Map My Tracks. There is no additional purchase necessary.
- You should create a randomised, anonymous username. We recommend not using your full name, email address or other identifiable characteristics.
- Let the research team know what your username is! This can be privately via messenger.
- Within Map My Tracks, you'll be added to an active 'event' – the Mapping Mobility event.
- Finally, login into the website Map My Tracks and set the privacy zone you are comfortable with. Note that no data will be collected within this privacy zone.

4. **Participating:**

When it is convenient for you, you should then begin recording the routes you take. You can use a 'tag' to differentiate between your mode of travel (i.e. bike, walk, scooter).

Every month, the research team will collate all the data that has been submitted by different users and anonymize the data. We will keep track of which users have submitted which routes, but this will not be visible to others.

The data is then published for others to use.

This section is only for those opting into the full citizen science training program.

5. **Citizen scientists – welcome!**

If you are reading this section, you are considering opting into the full citizen science training program. Welcome aboard! This program will provide you with introductory level skills in Geographic Information Systems (GIS). It will teach you the basic theory of GIS, how to use GIS software and equip you with the ability to continue your training independently! You will attend 3 x 2-hour workshops and complete 3 x 2-hour practicals. Workshops will be held at specific times, but you can complete the practicals at your own pace!

6. **Downloading QGIS**

It is important that your computer can handle the necessary software to complete the practicals. QGIS is a free, open source piece of software. Unfortunately, it is not available on

tablets or from any app stores. You will need a computer to participate. **QGIS can run on most computers or laptops. Smaller Notebooks and Chrome books will be unlikely to run QGIS. Given QGIS has no minimum specifications, it is difficult to know if it will run or not.**

You can read about QGIS here:

<https://qgis.org/en/site/>

(N.B. We recommend using some form of external storage (USB stick or hard drive) to store data for the practicals)

7. Installing QGIS

QGIS is a community built piece of software, which means it is developed by people like you! Sometimes, new versions are a bit buggy. We are going to be working on the latest 'stable release', where such bugs have been removed. **These practicals are design to run on a Windows operating system.** On the link below, you should scroll down and install version 3.16. (if you are unsure if your pc is 32 or 64 bit, here's a guide on how to check! <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/determine-whether-your-computer-is-running-a-32-bit-version-or-64-bit-version-of-the-windows-operating-system-aac162a1-0cb3-46f2-888f-2f22897396ce>)

Install QGIS using the recommended settings when prompted

Download link: <https://qgis.org/en/site/forusers/download.html>

Long term release repository (most stable):

	sha256	
	sha256	

This is the version you should download.

8. Getting ready to start!

Once QGIS is installed, you will be ready to begin the Citizen Science training program! Please let a member of the research team know. They will add you to the group of citizen scientists on Facebook

and the citizen science mailing list. Here you will be updated on workshop times, be sent practicals to complete and can ask the research team or other participants for help and advice! **Stay tuned!**

Thank you for reading this document. If you have any further questions, email
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